

The Reality of the Formative Assessment of Pupils' Level during the Physical Education Class in Light of the Competency-based Approach A Field Study of some Middle Schools from the Municipality of Bordj Bou Arreridj

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to know the reality of formative assessment of the pupils' level during the physical and sports education class in the middle school stage from the teachers' perspective. A questionnaire was given to a sample of 38 teachers of physical and sports education, chosen through a comprehensive inventory method from the municipality of Bordj Bou Arreridj. Following the descriptive approach, the main results obtained were as follows: There are statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($0.05 \geq$) - attributed to the scientific qualification variable - between the means of the sample-members' answers about the reality of the formative assessment of the pupils' level in light of the competency-based approach. The results were in favour of the teachers holding a Master's degree. The difficulties in implementing formative assessment are linked to the lack of training of the teachers of physical and sports education.

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I. Introduction

The teaching strategy in the subject of physical and sports education that is based on the competency-based approach has become the focus of all societies aspiring to promising future prospects that take their dynamic dimension from their conceptualisation of the individuals' competencies, and their abilities to deploy their beneficial knowledge and invest it in advancing their scientific and social levels (Keroum, 2010, 101).

Whereas, physical and sports education are one of the fertile fields in building the integrated individual from an emotional, cognitive and motor sense (Ahmed& Amira, 2017, 285)

Assessment during the physical and sports education class is an important factor in correcting the deviation that the professor may experience during the educational units through understanding, searching for and diagnosing problems, and then developing an alternative or appropriate remedial work. In many cases, however, a number of obstacles and difficulties, which we will highlight by standing on them in our study, may accompany the assessment process in the physical and sports education class, as well as knowing the extent of achieving goals, measuring the learner's ability and depicting the negative and positive sides (Al-okbi & Ben Kanab, 2017, 386).

Formative Assessment is also a process that takes place at the end of certain learning tasks with the aim of informing the pupil and the teacher about the degree of control obtained, and discovering the areas of difficulty the learner encounters through his learning, in order to allow him to discover the strategies that enable him to progress (Boutaba, 2011, 35).

In addition ,formative evaluation the competency-based approach is significant in understanding the extent to which ,the student's acquire the motor skills during the physical and sports *education* class, It also allows to reveal his strengths and weaknesses ,Therefore ,through this study,- we seek to know the reality of the formative evaluation of the students level during the physical education and sports class in light of the competency-based approach.

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Literature Review

A number of studies have dealt with the subject of formative assessment within the competency-based approach. Benci Mesaoud Lubna's study 2007-2008, intitled "The reality of assessment in primary education in light of the competency-based approach" -University of Constantine, aimed at identifying the reality of assessment in primary education in light of the competency-based approach. The study's questions focused on: What is the reality of assessment in primary education in light of the competency-based approach? What are the difficulties that primary education teachers face in implementing formative assessment? Relying on the descriptive approach, the researcher gave a questionnaire to a simple sample of 170 teachers, males and females. The main finding was that there are pedagogical difficulties in the implementation of formative assessment in the primary school, including the lack of teacher training and the insufficiency of the time allotted to the learning session.

Another study by Baabcha Badreddine 2016/2017 aimed at identifying the extent of the importance of assessment in the physical and sports education class in the secondary-education level; identifying and unveiling the difficulties that the teacher faces in the assessment process. The study's questions were as follows: Do physical education teachers rely on physical tests in the process of educational assessment? Do teachers face difficulties in the implementation of the assessment process? Relying on the descriptive approach, a questionnaire was given to a simple sample consisting of 25 secondary school physical education teachers. The researcher obtained the following results: Physical and sports education teachers rely on physical tests in the implementation of educational assessment and, in doing so, they face difficulties.

In the third study by Lamiya Hussein 2017/2018, the aim was identify the current reality of formative assessment in light of teaching with the competency-based approach at the secondary level, and, -to identify the differences between secondary education teachers in using the formative assessment in terms of variables (teaching subject, experience, and training), the study's questions were as follows: Are there any differences between secondary education teachers in using formative assessment in light of

teaching with the competency-based approach? The researcher relied on the survey method and a questionnaire was administered to a simple random sample consisting of 834 teachers of various educational materials in Tizi Ouzou secondary schools. the researcher obtained the following results: There are differences between secondary education teachers in the use of formative assessment in the light of teaching with the competency-based approach attributed to the variables: teaching subject, experience in teaching and training.

As for the fourth study, by Al-Rawadi, Fateh and others, 2018, it aimed at identifying the reality of the use of formative assessment methods in the Arabic Language subject by first-year teachers of middle school. The study's questions were as follows: Are there any differences between first-year teachers of middle school in the extent of their use of formative assessment methods in the Arabic Language subject attributed to the gender, academic qualification, and experience variables? The researcher relied on the descriptive approach on a simple random sample consisting of 30 male and female teachers of the Arabic Language who teach first year classes at the middle school were observed, The researcher obtained the following results: There are no differences between the middle school teachers of first-year classe in the extent of their use of formative assessment methods in the Arabic Language subject attributed to the variable of gender, academic qualification, and experience.

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This standpoint has led us to raise a general question:

- In light of the competency-based approach, what is the reality of the formative assessment of pupils' level during the physical education class from the teachers' point of view?

The following secondary questions were raised: Are there any statistically significant differences at a significance level of $\alpha 0.05 \geq$ about the reality of the formative assessment of pupils' level in light of the competency-based approach from the teachers' perspective due to the variables of gender, academic qualification and years of experience?

- What are the difficulties that the physical and sports education teachers face most in the formative assessment of pupils' level in light of the competency-based approach?

II. Method and Materials

- **The sample and the sampling procedure:** The research population included middle-school teachers of physical and sports education from the municipality of Bordj Bou Arreridj (38 teachers).

With regard to our research sample, all the members of the population have participated, meaning that we adopted a comprehensive inventory method in sample selection.

2.1 Procedures:

- **Method:** This study relied on the descriptive and analytical approach which clarifies the phenomenon under study, and analyses it with the aim of identifying strengths and weaknesses.

- **Defining the variables:**

- The independent variable: In our study, the independent variable is the one that affects the dependent variable and is defined as the "formative assessment of pupils' level."

- The dependent variable: In our study, it is the one that is affected by the independent variable, and it is defined as the "teaching through the competency-based approach."

2.2. Materials:

- The study tool and the scientific foundations: A questionnaire was used as a research tool. after reviewing many questionnaires from previous studies and quoting some of them, the questionnaire ended up by three sections:

The first section: It represents the data and personal information of the research sample, which included (03) elements represented in "gender, academic qualification, years of experience."

The second section: the axis of lack of training which: consists of (06) phrases

The third section: the axis of lack of time: which it consists of (06) phrases

The fourth section: the axis of the rise in the number of students: which consists of (06) phrases.

2.3. Design and Procedure

- **Scientific foundations of the instrument:**

- **Instrument validity:**

A-Face Validity:

The researchers presented the research tool (questionnaire) in its preliminary form to a group of experienced judges in the fields of scientific research, and qualified ones in the field of the study subject to check its validity. The two researchers asked the judges to express their opinion on the extent to which the terms of the study tool are clear, the extent to which they belong to the axis to which they belong, and their suitability to measure what they are set for, as well as adding or modifying any of the phrases and in light of the directions given by the judges, the researchers made the amendments agreed upon by most of the judges.

B - Internal consistency validity:

After checking the face validity of the study tool, the Pearson coefficient was used to verify the construct validity and internal consistency, and to determine the extent of its internal homogeneity.

B.1 The internal consistency between the statements of the formative assessment axis and the overall score obtained in this axis.

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Table 01: Correlation coefficients between each paragraph of the formative assessment reality axis and the total score of its paragraphs

Number	Phrase content	Correlation coefficient	Indication level
01	The training of physical education teachers serves to develop their formative assessment techniques	0.843	0.00
02	The training of physical and sports education teachers takes into account knowing the types of assessment	0.950	0.00
03	The training of physical and sports education teachers contributes to training in developing a plan for formative assessment	0.917	0.00
04	Training teachers of physical and sports education requires knowledge about the stages of formative assessment.	0.960	0.00
05	Training teachers of physical education and sports and knowing how to apply formative assessment.	0.874	0.00
06	The tools (means) of the formative assessment are taken into consideration during the training of the teachers of physical and sports education	0.920	0.00
07	The time allocated to the physical education and sports class and the formative assessment tools used.	0.963	0.00
08	The lack of time allocated to the physical education and sports class does not enable the formative evaluation.	0.945	0.00
09	Taking into account the time allocated to the physical education and sports class and individual differences during the formative evaluation.	0.971	0.00
10	The time allocated to the physical and sports education class contributes to the classification of pupils' mistakes.	0.962	0.00
11	The time allotted to the physical and sports education class allows for the correcting the errors of each student.	0.938	0.00
12	The time allotted to the physical and sports education class helps in conducting a formative assessment when moving from an individual to a group activity.	0.957	0.00
13	The high number of students in the class does not allow each pupil to know level of previously-acquired competency.	0.853	0.00
14	The big number of pupils in a class does not help in tracking each pupil's accomplishments.	0.918	0.00
15	The number of students in the physical and sports education class does not allow for to each student their mistake	0.928	0.00
16	The number of students physical and sports education class does not allow for correcting students' mistakes.	0.933	0.00
17	The large number of pupils does not allow for the formative assessment of students.	0.938	0.00
18	The number of students in the physical and sports education class does not help to ensure that each student achieves the learning objectives sought by the teaching process.	0.734	0.00

Source: Designed by the researchers based on the SPSS output, version 20
The table shows the correlation coefficients between each of the paragraphs of the formative assessment reality axis and the total score of its paragraphs, the correlation coefficients ranged between (0.734-0.963), which is considered significant at the level of significance (0.01-0.05).

Instrument reliability:

The researchers used the Cronbach coefficient to measure the reliability of the questionnaire, the value of the Alpha Cronbach coefficient of each axis of the questionnaire, and for the questionnaire as a whole was obtained Table (02) shows that:

Table 02: Cronbach alpha test results

Questionnaire axes	Number of paragraphs	Cronbach α
Formative Assessment	18	0.984

Source: Designed by the researchers based on the SPSS output, version 20

The value of the Cronbach alpha coefficient was high; it was equal to 0.984, which is considered a high reliability coefficient, Therefore the questionnaire is distributable, and the two researchers have confirmed the validity and the reliability of the study tool, which makes them fully confident of the validity of the results.

2.4. Statistical analysis:

The researchers used the statistical program SPSS (The Statistical Package for Social Sciences Edition 20)

III. Results

The answer to the first question: Are there any statistically significant differences at a significance level of $\alpha 0.05 \geq$ attributed to the variables of gender, academic qualification and years of experience about the reality of the formative assessment of pupils' level in light of the competency-based approach from the teachers' perspective?

3-1 The answer to the first question: Are there any statistically significant differences at a significance level of $\alpha 0.05 \geq$ attributed to the gender variable about the reality of the formative assessment of pupils' level in light of the competency-based approach from the teachers' perspective?

To answer this question, an independent samples t-test was used in order to find out the differences attributed to the gender variable. Table 05 shows the arithmetic means and standard deviations of the mean scores of the formative assessment of the pupils' level under the competency-based approach from the teachers' perspective. The table reports the (t) value and the level of its significance according to the gender variable at 36 degrees of freedom.

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Table 03. T-test results for the significance of the differences attributed to the gender variable between the arithmetic means of the sample members' responses about the reality of the formative assessment of the pupils' level in light of the competency-based approach from the teachers' perspective

Questionnaire Section	Gender	The Number	SMA	Standard Deviation	T-test Value	Significance Value	Significance Level
The reality of the formative assessment of pupils' level from the teachers' perspective	Male	06	49.50	8.21	-0.765	0.116	Not Statistically Significant
	female	32	55.18	17.70			

Source: Designed by the researchers based on the SPSS output, version 20

In the section of the reality of the formative assessment of the pupils' level in light of the competency-based approach from the teachers' perspective, the researchers have found that the value of the arithmetic mean of the female professors (N=06) was ($M=49.50$), with a standard deviation of ($SD=8.21$). For the male teachers (N=32), the arithmetic mean was ($M=55.18$) with a standard deviation of ($SD=17.70$). The calculated t value in this field was (-0.765) with a significance of (0.116).

By comparing this value to the level of significance ($0.05 \geq$), we find that it is higher than (0.05). This suggests that there are no statistically significant differences attributed to the gender variable about the reality of the formative assessment of the pupils' level in light of the competency-based approach from the teachers' perspective.

3-2 The answer to the second question: Are there any statistically significant differences at a significance level of $\alpha 0.05 \geq$ attributed to the scientific qualification variable about the reality of the formative assessment of pupils' level in light of the competency-based approach from the teachers' perspective?

To answer this question, a t -test was run in order to find out the differences attributed to the scientific qualification variable. In this respect, table 06 shows the arithmetic averages and standard deviations of the mean scores of the reality of formative assessment of pupils' level in light of the competency-based approach from the teachers' perspective, in addition to the t value and the level of its significance with 36 degrees of freedom.

Table 04. *T-test results for the significance of the differences attributable to the scientific qualification variable between the arithmetic means of the sample members' responses about the reality of the formative assessment of pupils' level in light of the competency approach from the teachers' perspective*

Questionnaire Section	Qualification	The Number	SMA	Standard Deviation	T-test Value	Significance Value	Significance Level
The reality of the formative assessment the pupils' level from the teachers' perspective	Licence	16	49.56	13.46	5.352	0.05	Statistically Significant
	Master's	22	79.50	3.83			

Source: Designed by the researchers based on the SPSS output, version 20

In the section of the reality of the formative assessment of the pupils' level in light of the competency-based approach from the teachers' perspectives, the researchers found that the value of the arithmetic mean of the teachers holding a bachelor's degree, the number of which is (N=16), was ($M=49.56$), with a standard deviation of ($SD=13.46$). For the teachers holding a master's degree, the number of which is (N=22), the arithmetic mean was ($M=79.50$), with a standard deviation of ($SD=3.83$). The calculated t value in this section was (5.35) with a significance level of (0.05).

By comparing this value with the level of significance ($0.05 \geq$), we find that it is lower than (0.05), and this suggests the existence of statistically significant differences attributable to the scientific qualification variable, about the reality of the formative assessment of the pupils' level in light of the competency-based approach from the teachers' perspective. These results are in favour of the teachers holding a master's degree whose arithmetic mean was statistically significantly higher than that of the teachers holding a BA degree.

3-3 The answer to the third question: Are there any statistically significant differences at a significance level of $\alpha 0.05 \geq$ attributed to the years of experience variable about the reality of the formative assessment of pupils' level in light of the competency-based approach from the teachers' perspective?

To answer this question, one-way analysis of variance test (Anova) was run. Table 7 displays the source of variance, the sum of squares, degrees of freedom, the "F" value, and the level of significance for the sample

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members' responses attributable to the years of experience variable (1-5 years, 5-10 years, 10 years and more).

Table 05. The results the one-way analysis of variance test of the differences attributed to the years of experience variable between the arithmetic means of the sample members' responses about the formative assessment of pupils' level in light of the competency-based approach from the teacher's perspective

Questionnaire Section	The Source of the Variance	Sum of Squares	Degrees of Freedom	Mean Squares	"F" Value	Significance Value	Significance Level
The reality of the formative assessment of the pupils' level from the teachers' perspective	Between Groups	768.8	2	384.40	1.42	0.254	Not Statistically Significant
	Within Groups	9451	35	270.02			
	Total	10219	37				

Source: Designed by the researchers based on the SPSS output, version 20

Based on the results displayed in the table after running the Anova test the results were as follows:

In this section of the reality of formative assessment of pupils' level in light of the competency-based approach from the teachers' perspectives, the researchers have found that, for the source of variance between groups, the sum of squares between groups was 768.8, with 384.40 mean of squares, while the sum of squares within groups was 9451, with a mean of squares of 270.02. The calculated F value was was ($F=42$) with a significance level of (0.254). By comparing this value with the significance level ($0.05 \geq$), we find that it is higher than (0.05). This suggests that, at the significance level ($0.05 \geq$), no statistically significant differences attributable to the years of experience variable were found between the arithmetic means of the informants' responses, in the section of the reality of the formative evaluation of the pupil's level in light of the competency-based approach from the teachers' perspective.

Accordingly: "There are no statistically significant differences at the significance level of ($0.05 \geq$) attributable to the years of experience variable between the means of the study sample responses about the reality of the formative assessment of the pupils' level in light of the competency-based approach from the teachers' perspective."

3-4 The answer to the fourth question: What are the difficulties that the teachers of physical and sports education face most in the formative assessment of the pupils' level in light of the competency-based approach?

To answer this question, the paragraphs of the difficulties in the formative assessment sections (lack of training - time insufficiency – big number of pupils) were analysed by ordering, in a descendent manner, the total arithmetic means and the total standard deviation of the sections' statements.

Table 08. *The arithmetic mean and standard deviation of the formative assessment difficulties sections (lack of training – time insufficiency – big number of pupils)*

The Number	The Sections	SMA	Standard Deviation	Ranking
01	Lack of training	3.36	1.08	01
02	Time Insufficiency	2.96	1.06	02
03	High number of pupils	2.70	0.97	03

Source: Designed by the researchers based on the SPSS output, version 20

Based on table 8, the following results from of the difficulties of the formative assessment sections are highlighted:

The section of lack of training ranked first with an arithmetic mean of ($M=3.36$) and a standard deviation of ($SD=1.08$), which is an acceptable score. It indicates that the difficulty of formative assessment of the pupils' level is attributed to the physical and sports education teachers' lack of training. On the other hand, the time insufficiency section was ranked second with an arithmetic mean of ($M=2.96$) and a standard deviation of ($SD=1.06$), which is a weak ratio as the time insufficiency does not significantly affect the formative assessment of the pupils' level. Concerning the section of the big number of pupils, it ranked last with an arithmetic mean of ($M=2.70$) and a standard deviation of ($SD=0.97$), which is a weak ratio, since the number of pupils does not significantly affect the formative assessment of the pupils' level during the physical and sports education class.

IV. Discussion

On the basis of the results presented so far, it can be said that there are no statistically significant differences attributed to the gender variable about the

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reality of the formative evaluation of the pupils' level in light of the competency-based approach from teachers' perspective. This is only indicative of the fact that formative assessment is not different for both genders; male and female teachers. The results match those obtained by Al-waraadi Fateh et al. 2018, which concluded that there are no differences attributed to the gender variable between middle-school teachers of the first year level in the extent of their use of formative assessment methods in the Arabic language subject.

It is also evident from the second hypothesis that there are statistically significant differences attributed to the scientific qualification variable about the reality of the formative assessment of the pupils' level in light of the competency-based approach from the teachers' perspective. The results were in favour of the teachers holding a master's degree, and this indicates that the latter use formative assessment more than the teachers holding a BA degree. The results obtained in this study differ from those found by Azza Ammar et al. (2012, p58) who concluded that there were no statistically significant differences between the teachers who graduated from university (the Higher School of Professors) and those who graduated from the Technological Institute of Education in the difficulty of their use of formative assessment.

As for the third hypothesis, it is shown that that there were no statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($0.05 \geq$) attributed to the years of experience variable between the means of the study sample's responses about the reality of the formative assessment of the pupil's level in light of the competency-based approach from the teachers' perspective. As such, the results come in line with those obtained by Al-waraadi Fateh et al. 2018, which concluded that there are no differences between the middle-school teachers in the extent of their use of formative evaluation methods in the Arabic language subject attributed to the variable of experience. However, the results do not match those reported in the study of Lamia Houcine 2017/2018, which concluded that there are differences between secondary education teachers in using the formative evaluation in light of the competency-based approach teaching attributed to the variable of experience.

As for the fourth hypothesis, “The difficulties of formative evaluation are attributed to the lack of training among the teachers of sports and physical education. The results match those found in Benci Mesaoud Lubna’s study (2008, p248), who concluded that the application of formative assessment in the elementary school faces pedagogical and organizational difficulties, including the lack of teacher training.

This is consistent with Baabcha Badreddine’s study 2016/2017, who found that physical and sports education teachers face difficulties in the implementation of educational assessment.

V. Conclusion

The formative assessment of the pupils’ level during the physical and sports education class in the middle-school stage is very important to gauge the extent of the pupils' response to the scheduled learning units. In light of what has been discussed so far, we arrive at the following results: There were no statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($0.05 \geq$), attributable to the variables of gender and years of experience, between the means of the study-sample members’ responses about the reality of the formative assessment of the pupils’ level in light of the competency-based approach from the teachers’ perspective. There were statistically significant differences at the level of significance (0.05) attributable to the academic qualification variable between the means of the study-sample members’ responses about the reality of the formative assessment of the pupils’ level in light of the competency-based approach from the teachers’ perspective. The results were in favour of the teachers holding a master’s degree whose arithmetic mean was significantly higher than that of the teachers holding a BA degree. In addition, the difficulties of formative assessment are also attributed to the lack of training of the sports and physical education teachers.

This is why we recommend that formative assessment should be implemented and given attention during the physical and sports education class by the teacher. Training sessions and seminars on formative

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assessment should be organised as well by the subject inspectors for the benefit of the physical and sports education teachers.

In addition, for the teacher to be able to effectively implement formative assessment, it is recommended that the time allotted to the physical and sports education session should be increased. Furthermore, educational resources and means need to be provided for the teacher in order to implement formative assessment at ease.

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